

Rice-based cropping systems

Rice varieties tested in interrows of first ratoon crops of sugarcane. Mauritius.

Upland rice in interrows of ratoon sugarcane in Mauritius

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Rice varieties were tested in interrows of first ratoon crops of sugarcane under irrigated and rainfed conditions (see photo).

The trials were sown at two sites on two dates under the conditions listed in Table 1.

Kwang Loo and Red Plum Zao had short growing cycles and matured well before the cane canopy had covered the interrows (Table 2). Kwang Loo yielded slightly lower than Red Plum. Chen Chui No. 11, a potentially high yielder, had a comparatively longer growing cycle and sometimes did not reach maturity before being shadowed by the cane canopy.

Yields in the rainfed trials may have been affected by strong winds and heavy rains during three cyclones near the island during the growth cycle. From the limited data, Red Plum showed promise for cane interrow cultivation under both irrigated and rainfed conditions. **W**

Table 1. Experimental conditions at Fuel and Benares, Mauritius.

Condition	Sites	
	Fuel	Benares
Altitude	125 m	100 m
Soil type	Low Humic Latisol	Low Humic Latisol
Soil pH	5.35	5.1
Cane variety	S 17	S 17
Spacing between cane rows	alternately 227 cm and 97 cm	alternately 227 cm and 97 cm
Rows of rice planted in every 227-cm cane interrow (photo)	4 rows, 20 cm apart	4 rows, 20 cm apart
Irrigation	Overhead	None
Planting dates		
First	9 Sept. 1976	1 Dec. 1976
Second	1 Oct. 1976	15 Dec. 1976

Table 2. Grain yield and other characteristics of rice varieties in interrows of sugarcane ratoons. Fuel and Benares, Mauritius.

Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Days to 50% flowering		Plant ht (cm)	
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2
<i>Fuel (irrigated)</i>						
Kwang Loo	1.4	1.0	83	80	50	52
Red Plum Zao	1.6	0.2 ^b	89	85	58	59
Chen Chui No. 11	1.6	0.2 ^b	97	97	68	70
<i>Benares (rainfed)</i>						
Kwang Loo	0.8	0.8	19	16	65	67
Red Plum Zao	0.9	0.8	79	76	68	71
No. 60	0.5	0.6	68	62	49	55

^aAt 12% moisture content. Twenty-six percent of the sugarcane field was used for rice cultivation.

^bSeverely damaged by buds.